

Complex Compounds of Substituted Thioureas. Part II. Mercury(II) Derivatives of *N*-Acetylthiourea

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With mercuric chloride and *N*-acetylthiourea, two compounds, mono- and bis-(*N*-acetylthiourea)-mercuric chlorides, have been obtained, whereas with mercuric iodide, only one such compound, the mono-(*N*-acetylthiourea) complex has been isolated. The constitution of these compounds has been discussed.

Five different types of thiourea complexes with mercuric ion have been described so far in the literature (cf. Beilstein's Handbuch), namely, those containing (a) four, (b) three, (c) two, (d) one, and (e) two-third molecules of thiourea, respectively, per mercuric ion. The complex compounds of substituted thiourea with mercuric ion have not so far been reported excepting $3\text{HgCl}_2 \cdot 2 \text{ etus}$ (etus represents ethylenethiourea), described by Hofmann (*Ber.*, 1873, 6, 598). It has now been found that *N*-acetylthiourea forms with mercuric chloride and mercuric iodide only complexes of the type (c), viz., $\text{HgCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{AcTh}$, and two others are of the type (d), viz., $\text{HgCl}_2 \cdot \text{AcTh}$ and $\text{HgI}_2 \cdot \text{AcTh}$ (AcTh represents *N*-acetylthiourea). The tendency for co-ordination of thiourea with mercuric ion seems to decrease in *N*-acetylthiourea.

Tetraco-ordination of the mercuric ion confers a stable radon structure to it and in conformity with this idea the tetra-, tri-, bis-, and mono-thiourea-mercuric complexes can be represented by (1) (II), (III), and (IV) respectively.

[S-U represents $\text{S}-\text{C} \begin{cases} \text{NHR} \\ \text{NHR} \end{cases}$. X=monovalent acid radical. R=R'=H atom or alkyl, aryl, or other organic radicals.]

The mercuric tetrathiourea chloride is soluble in water and hence has been represented as a salt as in (I), whereas all the compounds of tri-, bis-, and mono-thiourea types, described previously as also in the present paper, are fairly insoluble in water but soluble in organic solvents. Hence these have been represented to be non-electrolytes as in (II), (III), and (IV) respectively. The mono-thiourea-mercuric salts, represented as in (IV), are binuclear compounds with thiourea molecules serving as bridges.

With other metals thiourea complexes are known to be formed containing fractional molecules of thiourea per metal atom. Morgan and Burstall (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1928, 143) suggest that the $-NH_2$ groups of thiourea molecule may also take part in the co-ordination, thus enabling thiourea molecule to bridge two metal atoms. The present authors suggest that with the help of two lone pair of electrons, the S-atom of thiourea forms two co-ordination bonds with two different metal atoms, thus forming a bridge between them; the S-atom in such a thiourea bridge will become tetra-covalent. The bridging property of thiourea molecule is presumably manifested in the compound, $3HgCl_2 \cdot 2Setu$ (etu represents $C_2N_2H_4S$) described by Hofmann (*loc. cit.*) as shown in (V).

EXPERIMENTAL

All the reagents used were of analytical quality. *N*-Acetylthiourea was prepared by the method of Neucki (*this issue*, p. 647).

Mono-(N-acetylthiourea)-mercuric Chloride.—To a nearly ice-cold, saturated solution of *N*-acetylthiourea (1.2 g.) in anhydrous acetone (10 c. c.) was added a nearly saturated ice-cold solution of mercuric chloride (3 g.) in anhydrous acetone (10 c. c.). On keeping the mixture in a refrigerator for sometime, a white solid crystallised out, which was washed with ice-cold acetone solution (1:1) and then once with ice-cold anhydrous acetone. It was dried in air and analysed. (Found: N, 6.81; Cl, 17.33; Hg, 50.1. $HgCl_2 \cdot CH_3CONHCSNH_2$ requires N, 6.88; Cl, 17.4; Hg, 49.3%).

The substance is stable but with NaOH it decomposes forming mercuric sulphide. It is insoluble in water but fairly soluble in acetone.

Bis-(N-acetylthiourea)-mercuric Chloride.—A nearly saturated solution of mercuric chloride (1.4 g.) in acetone solution (1:1) was added slowly with stirring to a concentrated solution of *N*-acetylthiourea (2.4 g.) in the same solvent (mol. proportion 1:4). The white spongy precipitate thus formed was washed successively with acetone and ethanol. It was dried in air and analysed. (Found: N, 11.54; Cl, 14.33; Hg, 39.90. $HgCl_2 \cdot 2CH_3CONHCSNH_2$ requires N, 11.08; Cl, 14.02; Hg, 39.68%).

The same substance was obtained by taking mercuric chloride and *N*-acetylthiourea in the molecular proportion of 1:8 (in aqueous acetone medium), and 1:4 (in anhydrous acetone medium) and hence complexes containing more than two molecules of *N*-acetylthiourea per molecule of mercuric chloride probably do not exist. It resembles the previous compound in properties.

Mono-(N-acetylthiourea)-mercuric iodide was prepared from mercuric iodide (1 mole) and *N*-acetylthiourea (1 mole) in cold acetone solution. The mixture was kept at 0° for sometime and then on dilution with excess of ice-cold water, a white precipitate was formed which changed to yellow. It was filtered, washed with water, dried, and analysed. (Found: N, 5.00; I, 44.45; Hg, 35.59. $\text{HgI}_2 \cdot \text{CH}_3\text{CONHCSNH}_2$ requires N, 4.89; I, 44.34; Hg, 35.04%).

The same compound was obtained even by using an excess of *N*-acetylthiourea (1:2). Its properties resemble those of the corresponding chloro compound.

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